

Antenna Array Configurations for Terrestrial Backhaul Links At Ka-band Frequencies

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Abstract— The paper considers a backhaul network for Ka-band. In this band, antenna arrays must employ large number of elements with appropriate beamforming techniques to combat the severe path loss. The goal of this paper is to analyze massive antenna arrays under realistic considerations for the use in terrestrial backhaul links. This analysis addresses practical issues from the implementation point of view such as 3D array geometry, the minimum number of radiating elements needed to fulfill link budget requirements in backhaul links, distribution of radiating elements in a 3D array geometry and influence of realistic antenna patterns on beamforming capabilities of such arrays. The results indicate that a realistic backhaul scenario may require antenna arrays containing thousands of radiating elements. Selected simulation examples show that polarimetric beamforming is required in realistic scenarios especially when radiating elements do not have good cross polarization discrimination.

Index Terms—antenna array, backhaul link, beamforming, beam steering, null steering, polarimetric beamforming.

I. INTRODUCTION

The changes in user trends and new applications recently brought a substantial increase of mobile traffic. Different access network technologies such as heterogeneous networks, millimeter wave access, or massive MIMO have been proposed for such traffic demands.

In this paper we assume a backhaul network scenario followed by the EU H2020 project SANSa (Grant agreement no. 645047). Projects goals and the scenario are described in [1]. This project is focused on providing a solution for the backhaul of future communication systems to serve the increasing traffic demands. The SANSa solution is based on the development of enabling technologies for building a self-organizing hybrid terrestrial satellite backhaul network capable of reconfiguring the terrestrial topology and jointly exploiting the terrestrial and satellite links. The SANSa project aims at development of novel beamforming (BF) antennas, dynamic radio resource management and data-based shared access techniques for enabling the spectrum sharing among terrestrial and satellite segments at Ka-band frequencies. At these frequencies, high quality terrestrial communication links require massive antenna arrays that can provide large array gains by proper BF algorithms. Conventional BF techniques are performed in the baseband by means of digital signal processing. The full digital BF is not feasible for large antenna arrays at Ka-band frequencies as it would require thousands of radio frequency chains. This is unfeasible due to high implementation costs

and high energy consumption. Analog BF usually results in bulky and lossy BF networks that frequently suffer from the constant amplitude constraint [1]. To achieve better performance, hybrid analog-digital solutions were suggested e.g. in [3]-[7]. In our papers [6], [7], we focused on the digital step of the hybrid analog-digital BF. Our approaches exploit block diagonalization and MMSE techniques that require full channel state information (CSI) [6] or a partial CSI [7]. Performance of the proposed interference mitigation techniques was demonstrated in selected 2D scenarios by assuming isotropic radiating elements with perfect cross polarization discrimination (XPD). This is the usual approach in the majority of BF papers where the performance is demonstrated by using antenna arrays with constrained number of isotropic radiating elements. In order to bring the performance analysis closer to real life scenarios more realistic antenna structures must be employed. The goal of this paper is to analyze realistic antenna structures that are required for backhaul links at Ka-band frequencies. The paper addresses 3D antenna geometries, the minimum number of radiating elements, their distribution in a 3D antenna array and it illustrates effects evoked by the use of realistic antenna patterns in 3D scenarios.

Such scenarios require 3D antenna arrays containing elements distributed in all the three Cartesian dimensions like a stacked uniform antenna array (SUCA), or a sectorized planar antenna array (SUPA). A comparison of 3D array geometries can be found e.g. in [8]. This analysis assumed a single beam scanning in azimuth with only one active sector. In the case of SUCA, only a limited angle sector of the circular surface was active and it was incrementally shifted according to the beam direction. However, this comparison is not suitable for our scenario with self-organizing hybrid terrestrial satellite backhaul network which has to be capable of reconfiguring the terrestrial topology and protecting a satellite sector by proper interference mitigation techniques e.g. by steering nulls in necessary directions. The analysis presented in [8] does not take into account that the implementation of the incremental shifts for SUCAs requires a complex switching network, which quickly becomes unfeasible for large antenna arrays. Moreover, it does not take into account the null steering, the need for multiple simultaneous beams pointing to arbitrary directions and so the need to use all sectors in parallel. All these open questions are addressed in this paper.

II. SCENARIO DESCRIPTION

A terrestrial backhaul network with reconfigurable topology for shared frequency use of the 18 GHz satellite forward band and 28 GHz return band is considered. The interference mitigation techniques become mandatory in such scenario. The interference mitigation techniques are required to operate in different scenarios like rural, urban or maritime. The specifics of scenarios in terms of e.g. link distances, node densities, scanning ranges, etc. influence requirements that must be imposed on antenna arrays. Examples of scenario specific antenna requirements for a dense area node and for an end node in a rural scenario are described in [9]. Requirements relevant for this paper are listed below:

- The smart antenna must be capable to electronically steer multiple simultaneous beams (not only multicast) in order to enable self-organization of the hybrid terrestrial network which must be able to reconfigure its topology according to the instantaneous network status.
- This implies that the scanning range must be 360° in azimuth so that the whole plane is supported.
- The beam-width depends on the array gain and shall be e.g. 2° for 40dBi.
- The smart antenna must be capable to electronically steer nulls in order to mitigate potential interference to/from other terrestrial links and to/from satellite terminals with a certain null depth.
- Dense area nodes require an array gain from 19 dBi to 31dBi, a null from 22dBi to 55dBi below the array gain and an elevation scanning range from 4° to 26° .
- End nodes in a rural environment require an array gain from 26 dBi to 42 dBi, a null from 9 dBi to 54 dBi and elevation scanning from 0.1° to 10° .

For the dense area nodes, the 19 dBi antenna gain corresponds to a link distance of 200 m and an operational frequency of 17.7 GHz [9]. The 31 dBi antenna gain is estimated for the link distance of 1400 m and an operational frequency of 29.5 GHz. For the end node antennas, the 26 dBi antenna gain corresponds to the link distance of 1 km and an operational frequency of 17.7 GHz. The 42 dBi antenna gain is related to the link distance of 20 km and an operational frequency of 29.5 GHz. A more detailed explanation of other antenna requirements for the SANSA scenario such as the scanning range, beam-width, number of nulls, nulls depth, etc. can be found in [9].

III. BEAMFORMING WITH REALISTIC RADIATING ELEMENTS

BF papers usually suppose omnidirectional radiating elements with perfect XPD. However, a realistic radiating element requires a full polarimetric antenna pattern description, which may be specified e.g. by ϕ - and ϑ -polarization patterns. Fig. 1 gives an example of such an antenna pattern at an elevation of $\vartheta=80^\circ$ simulated by Viasat antenna systems SA in Switzerland for a single polarization slot antenna. The XPD in dB reaches even negative values

and the weak cross-polarization becomes dominant. This demonstrates that although a radiating element is designed just for a single polarization, it may transmit (or receive) EM waves with other polarizations as well. Therefore, the polarimetry property must be taken into account by BF algorithms for realistic scenarios. An example is shown in the next section.

Fig. 1. Antenna pattern of a slot antenna at elevation $\vartheta=80^\circ$ for both polarizations

Let consider the BF approach presented in [10]. Furthermore, a BF antenna array with N_A radiating elements that has to steer N_B beams in one polarizations and N_N nulls in both polarization to protect a transceiver with unknown polarization from interference is assumed. For the considered scenario, the weights $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ can be computed as

$$\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{S}_R = [\mathbf{1} \ \mathbf{0}], \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{1}^{1 \times N_B}$ denotes the all-one vector and $\mathbf{0}^{1 \times N_B + 2N_N}$ the zero vector. $\mathbf{S}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times (2N_B + 2N_N)}$ is a matrix where columns contain realistic steering vectors $\mathbf{s}_{R\phi}(\vartheta, \phi) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{R\vartheta}(\vartheta, \phi) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_A \times 1}$ for ϕ - and ϑ -polarization, respectively. They are associated with directions of beams $\vartheta_{B_i}, \phi_{B_i}$ and directions of nulls $\vartheta_{N_i}, \phi_{N_i}$

$$\mathbf{S}_R = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_{R\phi}^T(\vartheta_{B_1}, \phi_{B_1}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\phi}^T(\vartheta_{B_{N_B}}, \phi_{B_{N_B}}) \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\vartheta}^T(\vartheta_{B_1}, \phi_{B_1}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\vartheta}^T(\vartheta_{B_{N_B}}, \phi_{B_{N_B}}) \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\phi}^T(\vartheta_{N_1}, \phi_{N_1}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\phi}^T(\vartheta_{N_{N_N}}, \phi_{N_{N_N}}) \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\vartheta}^T(\vartheta_{N_1}, \phi_{N_1}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}_{R\vartheta}^T(\vartheta_{N_{N_N}}, \phi_{N_{N_N}}) \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2)$$

The first N_B columns of the matrix \mathbf{S}_R are related to the beam steering in the desired ϕ - polarization. The following N_B columns are associated with the beam steering in the unintended ϑ -polarization. The last $2N_N$ columns are dedicated to the null steering in both ϕ - and ϑ - polarization. The LS solution of (1) is given by

$$\mathbf{w}^H = [\mathbf{1} \ \mathbf{0}] \mathbf{S}_R^H (\mathbf{S}_R \mathbf{S}_R^H)^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

As the elements of the steering vector are weighted by an antenna radiation pattern the BF weights need to be normalized in order to remove this influence

$$\mathbf{w}_N = \frac{\mathbf{w}_D}{\mathbf{w}_D^H \mathbf{w}_D} \quad (4)$$

The following example illustrates the benefit of the polarimetric BF approach. An UCA equipped with 99 radiating elements is assumed with identical antenna radiation pattern, as shown in Fig. 1. The antenna spacing is equal to 0.39λ . According to [11] this spacing is suitable to keep small side-lobe levels of the correlation function. The antenna array shall form a beam at $(\vartheta=80^\circ, \phi=10^\circ)$ and a null at $(\vartheta=80^\circ, \phi=25^\circ)$. Fig. 2 depicts the beam pattern at the elevation of $\vartheta=80^\circ$.

Fig. 2. Polarimetric beam pattern of an UCA obtained by conventional BF without polarimetric constrictions

The BF weights were computed by an eight bit quantization of (4) in amplitude and phase. However in this example, the BF constrictions were imposed only on the dominant polarization similar to [10]. The constrictions on the weak polarization were omitted in the definition of \mathbf{S}_R in (2). As a result, the XPD at the direction of the null is only about -10dB. This means that if an antenna array is used at a transmitter and it produces a null in order to protect an unintended receiver, the receiver will not be protected. It will receive signals from cross-polarized waves that are 10dB stronger than the co-polarized waves. This can significantly influence the receiver performance, especially when a circularly polarized antenna is applied at the receiver. In order to transmit (receive) EM waves with only the dominant polarization and to protect other unintended receivers (be protected from interfering transmitters) by setting nulls, a polarimetric BF approach shall be used. Fig. 3 shows the influence on the beam pattern when the constrictions on the weak polarization are not omitted in the definition of \mathbf{S}_R in (2). In this case, the XPD at the beam and the null direction is improved by about 10dB and 20dB, respectively.

IV. 3D ARRAY GEOMETRIES

According to the requirements for antenna arrays in backhaul links described before, the antenna array has to cover 360° scanning range in azimuth and up to 26° in elevation. Simple 1D or 2D antenna arrays, such as uniform linear or planar arrays, cannot fulfill these requirements. 3D antenna arrays with dilatations in all the three spatial

Fig. 3. Polarimetric beam pattern of an UCA obtained by polarimetric BF

dimensions are required. This section provides estimation results for the smallest number of radiating elements for different 3D array geometries such that the BF requirements are fulfilled. The minimum number of elements was estimated for SUCA (Fig. 4) and SUPA (Fig. 5) having 4 and 5 sectors when all radiating elements are active. Antenna arrays with only one active sector are less suitable for our scenario where each base station may transmit multiple data streams to neighboring base stations distributed around it.

Fig. 4. UCA in xy-plane equidistantly stacked in z-direction

Fig. 5. Sectorized UPA with equiangular orientation

The BF requirements that affect the number of radiating elements are the array gain and the beam-width. The null depth depends on the quantization level and the phase noise of the array components. The inter-element distance of the array is assumed to be 0.5λ in the horizontal plane for the SUPA and 0.39λ for the SUCA. In this plane the antenna array is supposed to scan a beam in all directions. In the vertical plane, the antenna spacing can be enlarged due to the limited scanning range requirements in the elevation. The array gain mainly depends on the overall number of antenna elements and only slightly on their distribution among the horizontal and vertical plain. However, this distribution influences the beam-width in elevation and azimuth. The minimum number of elements and their distribution between xy-plane and the z-axis was estimated as follows:

- the total number of radiating elements was determined according to the required array gain,
- the number of elements in the xy-plane was set

according to the beam-width in azimuth,

- the number of elements in z-direction was obtained by dividing the total number of elements by the number of elements in the xy-plane,
- the antenna spacing in z-direction was determined by the scanning range in elevation,
- the beam-width in elevation was estimated according to the antenna spacing and number of antenna elements in elevation by simulations.

As the required array gain and the scanning range in elevation depend on the application scenario, the minimum number of elements was separately estimated for a node in a dense area and for an end node in a rural environment.

For a dense area node, the minimum number of radiating elements was estimated for an array gain equal to 31dBi. For such a gain, [9] defines the maximum beam-width in azimuth to be smaller than 6° . This value was used to determine the minimum number of elements in xy-plane and subsequently the number of elements in z-direction. The antenna spacing in z-direction was determined for a scanning range in elevation equal to 26° . TABLE I. lists the estimated number of radiating elements and the BF performance in terms of the gain and the beam-width in ϕ (BW_ϕ) and ϑ (BW_ϑ) for 4-SUPA (SUPA having 4 sectors), 5-SUPA and SUCA. The table also indicates that the achieved gain and the beam-width in azimuth and elevation vary for different antenna geometries. It also reflects their angle dependence. For example, the array gain is smaller when the beam steers towards edges of sectors and is higher for boresight directions of the SUPA sectors (UPAs).

TABLE I. ARRAY SIZES FOR A DENSE AREA NODE

Geometry	Elements per sector		Elements per array	Gain [dBi]	BW. [$^\circ$]	BW. [$^\circ$]
	xy	z				
4-SUPA	35	12	1680	31.0-33.8	3.8-6.0	8.0-9.4
5-SUPA	31	9	1395	31.0-32.5	3.8-6.0	8.8-11.2
SUCA	115	12	1380	31.0-32.2	5.4-6.0	8.4-9.4

TABLE II. shows the required number of antenna elements and the BF performance for the end area node. The minimum number of radiating elements was estimated for the minimum array gain equal to 42dBi. For such a gain [9] defines the maximum beam-width in azimuth to be smaller than 2° , which determines the number of elements in xy-plane and subsequently the number of elements in z-direction. The antenna spacing in z-direction was estimate for the scanning range in elevation of 10° .

TABLE II. ARRAY SIZES FOR AN END AREA NODE

Geometry	Elements per sector		Elements per array	Gain [dBi]	BW. [$^\circ$]	BW. [$^\circ$]
	xy	z				
4-SUPA	100	41	16400	42.0-43.7	1.4-2.0	~ 2.8
5-SUPA	98	29	14210	42.0-42.5	1.2-2.0	~ 2.8
SUCA	315	43	13545	42.0-42.2	~ 2.0	~ 2.0

It is possible to see that the large arrays gain resulted in high increase of the radiating antenna elements for all structures.

V. SIMULATION EXAMPLES

The following scenario is assumed to illustrate the shape of the array patterns for the estimated number of antenna elements and their distribution in a 3D array. In the dense area scenario a base station equipped with 4-SUPA has to steer a beam to another terrestrial base station which is at $(\vartheta=64^\circ, \phi=45^\circ)$. It has to protect a VSAT at $(\vartheta=80^\circ, \phi=45^\circ)$ which operates at the same frequencies. Therefore, 4-SUPA has to steer a null at the corresponding direction. This scenario is depicted in Fig. 6. The beam steering direction represents the worst case for SUPA with 4 sectors. The ϕ -angle ($\phi=45^\circ$) correlates with the border of two sectors and the ϑ -angle ($\vartheta=64^\circ$) correlates with the maximum scanning angle in elevation which is 26° (boresight at elevation 90° minus beam at elevation 64°). Therefore, the lowest array gain and the broadest beam in azimuth are expected. For the null steering the simulated scenario is challenging as well. The null is placed at the same azimuth and its position only differs in the elevation. For this scenario, BF weights were computed by 8 bit quantization of (4) in phase and amplitude. The BF constrictions were imposed on the dominant and the weak polarization in definition of \mathbf{S}_R in (2).

Fig. 6. Simulation scenario for beam and null steering

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 illustrate the azimuth cut at $\vartheta=64^\circ$ and the elevation cut at $\phi=45^\circ$ of the polarimetric array pattern obtained for 4-SUPA. The beam is zoomed to allow better estimation of the array gain and the beam-width. It can be observed that the array gain of about 31dB, the 3dB beam-width in azimuth of about 6° and elevation of about 8° correspond to results presented in TABLE I.

Fig. 7. Azimuth cut at $\vartheta=64^\circ$ of the polarimetric pattern for 4-SUPA

Fig. 8. Elevation cut at $\phi=45^\circ$ of the polarimetric pattern for 4-SUPA

For comparison, the performance of SUCA is illustrated in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. Since SUCA does not have sectors its performance does not depend on selection of the azimuth angle. The beam steering direction is ($\vartheta=64^\circ$, $\phi=5^\circ$) and it only correlates with the maximum scanning range in elevation in the assumed dense node scenario. The direction of the null is correspondingly set to the azimuth direction of the beam and the null is steered to ($\vartheta=80^\circ$, $\phi=5^\circ$). The array gain of about 31dB, the 3dB beam width in azimuth of about 6° and elevation which is about 8.4° correspond to results presented in TABLE I. In comparison to SUPAs the side lobes of SUCA are more smoothly distributed and are lower especially in the azimuth cut.

Fig. 9. Azimuth cut at $\vartheta=64^\circ$ of the polarimetric pattern for SUCA

Fig. 10. Elevation cut at $\phi=5^\circ$ of the polarimetric pattern for SUCA

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The paper investigated 3D antenna array structures that are necessary for backhaul links at Ka-band frequencies. The

paper provides the reader a feeling about the antenna array dimensions and an insight into their BF capabilities. If e.g. 18 GHz satellite forward band is aimed for sharing with terrestrial backhaul links then a suitable SUCA is only about 14cm high and 24cm in diameter large for dense area nodes.

Note that this simulation illustrates just the performance of the analog antenna array. Here, the null depth is dictated by the quantization of the BF weights. Therefore, relatively high number of bits was used in the simulation. The null depth can be improved by the use of hybrid analog-digital structure which is not illustrated by this example and definitely represents a future research topic in this area.

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